

1 **USP deubiquitinase function is likely required in the human embryo during differentiation to the**
2 **trophectoderm.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 deubiquitinases from the USP family as lineage commitment cooperating molecules in embryonic stem
10 cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Jin, J., Liu, J., Chen, C., Liu, Z., Jiang, C., Chu, H., Pan, W., Wang, X., Zhang, L., Li, B. and Jiang,
13 C., 2016. The deubiquitinase USP21 maintains the stemness of mouse embryonic stem cells via
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